

METHODS OF USING MODERN PEDAGOGICAL METHODS OF TEACHING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11542176>

Abstract. In this article, the methodology of reading in primary grades should work as a methodology of literary education, reading in primary grade should be taught as a preparatory subject for the systematic course of teaching literature, the methodology of the future primary grade A word about the fact that the teacher is able to approach the content of literary education and its teaching independently, not only to learn the experience of others, but also to be able to consciously analyze the results of their activities and draw the right conclusions. is conducted.

Key words: education, literary analysis and interpretation, didactic rule, deduction, induction, methodology, pedagogical technology, "Boomerang technology", "Saw" method.

Until now, literary education has been studied as part of the mother tongue teaching methodology. As the methodology of teaching literature in general secondary education has its own status as an independent science, it is an attempt to scientifically and methodically justify the fact that Methodist scholars should consider the methodology of literary education in primary education as an independent science of methodology.

It is known that in the second half of the 20th century, the idea of studying the artistic work as a work of art with an aesthetic approach to the work of art was put forward in the methodology of the primary school, while psychological research is a different approach to introducing the world of literature to the potential ability of young students. demands. For example, N.N. Svetlovskaya developed the theory of independent reading of the student, Ye.A. Adamov, M.S. Vasileva, V.G. Goretsky, M.I. Omorokov, T.G. Ramzaeva and others analyzed the form and content of the artistic work, L.A. Gorbushina, O. V. Kubasova , L.N. Mali, L.V. Nefedova and others noted the need to develop the creative works of students, and some of them, in the methodology developed by them. Thus, the methodology of primary education passed the stages of formation as a methodical science. It is known that aesthetic education of a person in connection with reading works of art, i.e. imparting knowledge, educating and

forming beliefs; that is, the tasks of studying children's literature samples as works of art, like the subjects taught at school, are assigned to reading classes.

As each subject has its own learning object and subject, nowadays the idea that the method of reading in primary classes should work as a method of literary education is being promoted. In fact, the methodology of reading as a preparatory subject for a systematic course of teaching literature defines its goals and tasks based on examples of children's literature. Based on this, it is appropriate to define the learning object of primary school reading classes as the process of students' acquisition of literary education.

The term "literary education" includes three interrelated processes:

1. personality education in the process of contact with literary and artistic works
2. teaching, that is, teaching children's literature as one of the school subjects
3. formation of personal development.

"Why should you teach?" developed by V.V. Golubkov. (purpose of teaching a work of art), "What should be taught?" (the content of literary education), "How to teach?" (the purpose, content, appropriate methods and methods, tools of the students - the future teacher), "Why is it necessary to teach this way and not otherwise?" (scientific basis of the chosen path) is based on the methodology of literary education. In today's methodology, this issue is considered from the point of view of the student. According to it, the following is defined as the learning goal recognized by the student:

1. "What am I learning?" (the content of literary education received by the student)
2. "How do I study?" (which methods of mastering the child uses)
3. "Why am I learning this way and not another way?" (understanding which of the learning methods is effective)

The development of methodology as a science is evident in teaching based on the connection of one paradigm with another. "Why does a teacher teach?", "Why does a child study?" the answers to the questions match.

First grade student cannot set himself the goals of filling in the gaps and mastering the art of speech. The teacher puts these goals in the middle and directs the students towards them. What are you reading? Think, why are we reading this work? Were you able to master this work well with our current method of reading and analysis?

Later, during the lessons, the student learns what he needs to know to become a reader, that a good book creates different experiences (care, anxiety) in the reader, encourages him to think, and allows him to choose his own position.

Currently, elementary school teachers expect clearly proven, scientifically based instructions from the methodology. The methodology allows the future elementary school teacher to be able to independently consciously approach the content of literary education and its teaching, not only to study the experience of others, but also to consciously analyze the results of their activities and make the right conclusion. ensures that they can die.

M.A. Rybnikova cites 4 didactic rules as the basis of the methodology:

1. Education should have a comprehensive impact on students' understanding.
2. Pupils clearly understand the problem set before them.
3. A methodist should have the ability to demonstrate new complex phenomena as easily as familiar ones.
4. Connecting deduction with induction.

M.A. Rybnikova considers this methodical system as a living process and emphasizes that the main attention should be paid to the methodical system.

These views require a new approach to the analysis and interpretation of literary and artistic works studied in primary school reading classes. Conducting the analysis of the work on the basis of step-by-step consistency allows to direct the educational activities of students to a specific time.

The use of pedagogical technologies such as the "Boomerang technology", the "Saw" method, the teaching material - the orientation of the work on the artistic work to a specific goal, the step-by-step organization of educational activities, individual approach to learners, students provides monitoring and rapid assessment of activities.

The artistic text studied in the "Saw" method is divided into components. This technology can be applied to the study of all works included in the "Reading Book" textbook in the 4th grade. For example, in the lesson where the story "Childhood of the Prince" is studied, the work is first played on audio. The work is divided into 4 parts. Students are also divided into 4 small groups. Each group will be assigned a reading section. The same task is given to each group.

In the teaching of modern literary education, the young generation growing up before the school should acquire the culture that was created hundreds of years ago during the history of mankind and has been filled up to this time, prepare

the child for real life, achieve a conscious choice of profession, make the students with the people around them. demands to be taught civilized behavior. For this, it is necessary to determine the main goals of school literary education at each stage of education, taking into account the capabilities and main activities of students.

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